

agar at 25 °C for 4 d to use as inocula. Plants of rice cultivar IR36 were inoculated at both seedling and early maturity stages. Lesion appearance and size were observed to determine their virulence.

Three pathogenic sclerotia-producing fungus pathogens — *Rhizoctonia solani*, *R. oryzae-sativae*, and *R. oryzae* were identified. The frequencies of the inoculum extracted from the soil were 57.3% for *R. solani*, 42.3% for *R. oryzae-sativae*, and 0.4% for *R. oryzae* (see table).

Tests for pathogenicity indicated that *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were more aggressive on rice than *R. oryzae-sativae*. They infected rice plants at both seedling and adult stages; *R. oryzae-sativae* infected plants only at the adult stage. Symptoms caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were similar, but *R. oryzae* caused dark reddish brown or brown margins. The lesions caused by *R. solani* and *R. oryzae* were also much

Distribution of sclerotial populations responsible for sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. IRRI, 1985.

Site and population	<i>R. solani</i>		<i>R. oryzae-sativae</i>		<i>R. oryzae</i>	
	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)	no.	Frequency (%)
C14						
Population A	111	53.6	96	46.4	—	—
Population B	110	52.1	101	47.9	—	—
Combined	221	52.9	197	47.1	—	—
B40						
Block A						
Apr	67	53.6	57	45.6		10.8
May	57	64.8	30	34.1	1	1.1
Block B						
Apr	74	65.5	38	33.6	1	0.9
May	64	64.7	35	35.3	—	—
Total or av	483	57.3	357	42.3	3	0.4

larger than those by *R. oryzae-sativae*, which were aggregated small spots.

We concluded that *R. solani* is the major causal organism of sheath diseases of rice in the tropics. Although less aggressive on rice than the two other fungi, *R. oryzae-sativae* was a

relatively large part of the entire sclerotial population found and may play an important role in causing rice sheath diseases in tropical areas. *R. oryzae* is very virulent on rice, but its sclerotial population was relatively low. □

Effect of plant age at inoculation on rice tungro virus development

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Twenty 10- to 20-d-old plants of variety TN1 were inoculated using 5 green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* per plant after 24-h acquisition feeding.

Susceptibility was high in 10-d-old plants, with percentage of infection decreasing with increased plant age (see

Relationship between plant age, infection (%), and incubation period.

figure). The negative correlation between plant age and infection percentage was highly significant. Mean incubation

period progressively increased with plant age. These two factors were positively correlated. □

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa, India

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Rice, the principal crop of Orissa, is grown in habitats ranging from fully rainfed unbanded uplands to deepwater situations with more than 50 cm water for the major part of the year.

Deepwater situations exist not only in the coastal belt at mean sea level (MSL) but also at altitudes as high as 1,067 m above MSL in the interior districts. The varieties grown under such situations are all local and take more than 180 d to mature.

In a survey of plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater

Plant parasitic nematodes associated with deepwater rice in Orissa India.

Nematode species	Frequency (%)	Density
<i>Aphelenchoides besseyi</i>	25	L
<i>Helicotylenchus dihystra</i>	20	L
<i>H. crenacauda</i>	25	L-M
<i>Hemicriconemoides cocophilus</i>	5	L
<i>Hirschmanniella mucronata</i>	65	M-H
<i>H. oryzae</i>	5	M
<i>Hoplolaimus indicus</i>	15	L
<i>Meloidogyne</i> sp.	5	H
<i>Pratylenchus zeae</i> ^b	10	L

^a L < 100 nematodes/250 ml soil, M = 100-250 nematodes/250 ml soil, H > 250 nematodes/250 ml soil. ^bNew record.

rice in Cuttack, Balasore (coastal belt), and Koraput (high altitude) districts, nine species were found (see table).

Hemicriconemoides cocophilus and *Pratylenchus zeae* were prevalent in the

basal root area in deepwater situations, *Hirschmanniella mucronata* in the nodal roots, and a *Meloidogyne* sp. in typical deepwater situations. *H. cocophilus* had

earlier been found in the rice rhizosphere in 50 cm water.

Of the rice plant samples, 25% were symptomless carriers of the white-tip

nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi*; 3 samples with ultra symptoms (1 from Cuttack and 2 from Balasore) did not yield *Ditylenchus angustus*. □

Disease occurrence as affected by age of transplanted seedlings

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Rice seedlings are usually transplanted at 20-25 d after sowing. Seedlings more than 30 d old recover more slowly than younger seedlings, especially if they have stem or root injury.

We studied diseases of IR18348 to assess the severity of infection by age of seedlings. Treatments with 20-d, 25-d, and 30-d seedlings were in a randomized complete block design replicated 3 times. Seeds were sown together in a wet bed, but transplanting was staggered according to seedling age. Standard cultural practices, except for pesticide application, were followed.

All diseases that occurred from seedling to maturity were identified and percentage incidence and severity of infection assessed. Sample plants were

Table 1. Percent infection and severity of diseases observed in IR18348 by age of seedlings. Cotabato, Philippines.

Seedling age (d)	RTV infection (%)	Severity (%)			
		BS	NBS	ShB	FSm
20	13.8	4.9	19.2	17.2	1.4
25	15.0	4.8	18.5	9.7	0.7
30	20.0	4.5	19.5	17.2	0.9

Table 2. Grain yield of IR18348 by age of seedlings. Cotabato, Philippines.

Seedling age (d)	Mean grain yield ^a (kg/5 m ²)
20	2.07 b
25	2.42 a
30	2.03 b

^a Means of 4 replications. Significant at the 5% level by DMRT.

taken from the middle rows of each plot. For foliar diseases, 5 leaves from 25 sample tillers taken at random in an X pattern were rated. Percentage infection and grain yield were recorded from plants in a 3-m² area.

Five diseases — tungro (RTV), brown spot (BS), narrow brown spot (NBS), sheath blight (ShB), and false smut (FSm) — were observed in IR18348, regardless of seedling age. Only RTV

Inoculum distribution patterns of rice sheath blight (ShB)

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Rice ShB caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* has become a major production-limiting disease in some localities in recent years. Sclerotia of *R. solani* formed on infected plants and dislodged on the field have been considered a primary source of inoculum. Avoidance of fields with high inoculum densities could reduce losses, but this requires knowing the spatial pattern of inoculum and diseased plants. Accurate, reliable sampling methods are needed to determine that.

We sprayed two ricefields (C14 and B40) at IRRI Jan-Aug 1985 on the basis of ShB incidence in previous cropping. The fields were divided into contiguous quadrats. Soil samples were collected with a 5-cm-diam soil sampler after harvest in C14 and both after harvest and after land preparation in B40. Samples from each quadrat were processed separately and numbers of sclerotia counted.

Mean number of sclerotia, standard deviation, and ratio of variance to mean were calculated for each field and each sample date. Four statistical probability distribution models — Poisson, negative binomial, Neyman type A, and Thomas double Poisson — were used for data analysis; goodness of fit was tested by chi-square.

was of major importance.

Percentage infection of RTV and disease severity of NBS, BS, ShB, and FSm did not vary significantly (Table 1).

However, 30-d seedlings had the highest NBS severity and 20-d seedlings had the lowest RTV percentage.

Seedlings transplanted at 25 d after sowing had the highest grain yield (Table 2). □

Disease incidence in each quadrat was calculated at early maturity, following Hashiba's equation

$$D = (1.62X - 32.4)A/100$$

where *D* is disease severity, *X* is the ratio of height of the uppermost lesion to total plant height, and *A* is percentage affected hills. Seven simulated sampling paths were compared with the quadrat method used.

R. solani sclerotia distribution patterns were clumped and best described by Thomas double Poisson and Neyman type A models. The variance to mean ratios of diseased plants found were significantly greater than unity, indicating that plant distribution did not coincide with the distribution patterns of sclerotia. Disease incidence was probably influenced by wind direction.

Comparison of the quadrat method and seven Simulated sampling paths indicated that sampling path depended on the degree of clustering of inoculum in the fields. No single sampling path provided the best estimate of sclerotial populations. But the distance between samples could be increased to cover a larger area to retain a minimum number of samples without losing accuracy. □

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